

The Interface between the Influence of Social Media on ESL Learners and the English Language Learning

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Abstract: The goal of this qualitative study, which used a case study approach, was to find out how social media affects English language acquisition in South India. Secondary school students, language educators, teachers in both private and public schools and universities, ESL instructors, and a practitioner of Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages were among the ten members of this assessment, who were purposefully chosen. The information gathered from the participants through written interviews utilising the Strengths - Weaknesses - Opportunities - Threats (SWOT) matrix is what determines the outcome. According to the findings of this study, social media provides numerous advantages or chances in English language acquisition in general. Their few traps and risks, on the other hand, have become arguably the most crucial issue and have produced impediments to learning the language. These internet-based social media sites, according to this study, might be useful platforms for providing up-to-date information, a considerable amount of language input, communication with native language speakers, and front-line learning. By and large, these social media platforms may lead to dishonesty, unscholarly and grammatical material, obscenities, and generic cooperation among language students. This study also brought to mind several practical applications of social media in English language instruction. The researcher also gave suggestions for future study opportunities on this issue.

Keywords: English language, Social Media, SWOT Matrix, Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats.

I. INTRODUCTION

Social media has been steadily affecting people's ways of life in a variety of ways, including communication, knowledge exchange, commerce, and education (Bhatti, Bano, & Rehman, 2019; Bhatti, 2018). With the growing popularity of various web-based social networking sites and other connected stages, academics and scholars from many areas are flocking to these sites (Akram, Shaheen, Bhatti, & Rehman, 2020). Continue to regard them as a focus topic that should be researched further. The impact of social media on second language acquisition and learning has been seen by language experts and teachers in particular. In a recent study, it was determined that a group that received learning, dedication, and motivation through a social networking website performed better on an English proficiency exam than a group that received training in in-person mode (Wamba, 2016).

Despite the fact that social media has an inextricable impact on people's lives everywhere, and considering that today's students are resistant to traditional teaching and learning techniques (Bosch, 2009), there are few studies that investigate their effects in education, particularly in English language learning (ELL). This study intends to add to the continuing discussion on the influence of social media in second language acquisition by focusing on numerous theories such as

Input Hypothesis, Social Interactionist, Constructivism, Cooperative Learning, Web-based Learning, and PC generated Instructions (Bhatti & Rehman, 2019). The analyst aims to evaluate the strengths, flaws, possibilities, and dangers of social media in language learning by using a SWOT analysis model and combining people's perspectives whose participation is direct in the field.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW (RELATED STUDIES)

The goal of this study is to look at various second language acquisition (SLA) theories and learning models. These SLA theories are thought to be capable of discussing the many subjects and themes in this research. This study is based on SLA theories or similar studies, such as Social-interactionist, Constructivism, Cooperative Learning, Web-based learning, and Computer-produced instructions. Social media is such a broad concept that it can't be defined in a single way. Individuals have generally characterised online life as A web-based consumer-generated collaboration of knowledge (Xiang 2012); A "gathering of the Internet- put together applications that work concerning the ideological and innovative establishments of Web, and that permit the creation and trade of User Generated Content," despite the term's lack of specialised significance." (Haenl and Kaplan, 2010) Furthermore, "material, words, photographs, recordings, and other works created with the intention of being shared." (Evans, 2012).

Regardless of the definitions used, the phrase "sharing" will never be appropriate to describe it. The proximity of contact, trading, sharing, mutual relationships, groups, and the like is widely considered as the context of social media work (Saad, Gbadebo, & Bhatti, 2019). Despite the fact that online networking instruments or stages are questionable, adaptable, and varied, a few researchers choose to organise these long-distance informal communication destinations according to their usual capacities (Bhatti, Salimon, & Saad, 2019).

These online networking apps, tools, and sites were categorised into more broad categories for communication, collaboration, training, and entertainment, specifically for Social systems administration, publish, photo sharing, audio, video, microblogging, livecasting, virtual universes, gaming, productivity apps, aggregators, rich webpage design, search, mobile, and relational (Brake and Safko, 2009). Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, MySpace, Blogger, Wikipedia, Flickr, Picasa, iTunes, YouTube, Twitter, Second Life, World of Warcraft, Google Docs, Digg, RSS 2.0, Yahoo! Search, Google Search, Jott, and Skype are examples of well-known online networking tools that fall under these categories. Indians have been expressing a "overwhelmingly substantial" presence in social media through going to the previously stated site or applications, among other Middle Eastern countries (Steckman and Andrews, 2017).

Individuals acquire accustomed with the language by their presenting of information or interpreting publications, according to Krashen's (1985) Input Hypothesis. When a person has access to a large amount of intelligible material, he or she is more likely to correctly learn and convey the language. In light of the fact that this examination is genuine, Iraqis must be overflowing with a significant amount of input by reading different methods such as social media, where English is widely used (Rehman, Bhatti, Shaheen, & Akram 2020). Language students are likely to understand the correspondence procedure and get off the language in web journals and microblogging destinations, social systems, proficient systems, video sharing systems, and substance driven networks thanks to the 330 extraordinary Web-based projects completed by the end of 2012 (Walaski, 2013).

However, with such a vast and content-overflowed route, people must find out how to channel the data they get in order to obtain scholarly and appropriate information.

During the late 1970s, Vygotsky created the social constructivism hypothesis. It emphasises that language is more intrapersonal than interpersonal, and it highlights the role of others in learning (Vygotsky, 1978, as referred to in Jones and Brader-Araje, 2002). Through these collaborations, social media has made language study and acquisition much more accessible through various online organisations and communication opportunities. The vocabulary or language of youngsters is a direct result of their exposure to their surroundings.

The theory of social interactionists is that language acquisition occurs when children naturally connect with more language capable adults (Lambert and Rudd, 2011) through "physical, verbal, cognitive, and social" aspects (Reutzel and Cooter, 2004). Even yet, one shortcoming of this idea is that when an individual connects with others and receives off base and unseemly language from others, or in social media. The Internet's intuitive concept plays a significant influence in establishing an extraordinarily open linguistic context or state (Black, 2005).

Non-native language speakers who participate in online groups and networks and attend speeches are likely to be exposed to the native language in interactions with native language speakers and are preoccupied with a variety of topics. In most discourse networks, socialisation allows linguistic "fledglings" to learn from those who are "experienced" (Duff, 2002).

Language acquisition through socialising is more than just an exchange of meaningful and syntactically consistent dialogues on social media sites. It also covers a wide range of social issues.

Language socialisation is defined as "the process of learning how to use language in socially and practically appropriate, locally meaningful ways, and as a means of connecting with others in the course of, without a doubt, the formation of everyday interactions and exercises." (Garrett, 2008) Indeed, the effect of online life is becoming increasingly obvious even in internet gaming networks. Pena and Hancock (2006) looked at the socio-emotional messages that online network video players exchange in a virtual environment. Regardless of whether they were in a "battle" scenario, the participants sent more positive socioemotional messages than negative ones. The more rookie players interacted with advanced players, the more they learned about the language socialisation process. Teachers are now considering learning modalities that promote second language acquisition and learning (Thorne, 2008), systematic thinking, and free learning as a result of the spotlight that virtual settings provide (Malerba, 2011). However, 'trash-talking,' or the use of profane language, is becoming more common among certain teens these days.

Web 2.0's framework allows anybody to share and participate in an increasingly straightforward manner (Grimes and Warschauer, 2007). For example, many people use Youtube not just as a video-sharing site, but also as a place to connect and network for both native and non-native language users. In language learning, the ability of clients to "operate together, make an offer" is essential (Lord and Lomicka, 2009). Social media, like other internet networks and gaming sites, is benefiting from the current era. According to a poll (Nielsen, 2010, as cited by Malerba, 2011), social networking sites accounted for a considerable share of the hours spent online. With over 175 million worldwide users, Facebook is one of the most popular long-distance interpersonal communication sites, allowing people from all over the world to interact and share culture, information, and language (Harrison and Thomas, 2009). The approach that clarifies the theme of language acquisition in the social organising site is once again the notion of social association. The importance of "intercession" in the development of human learning is crucial from the standpoint of social interactionism (Feuerstein, et.al, 2003). In most interpersonal interaction settings, these mediators or "more proficient others" are the ones who assist others in learning. Similarly, according to Feuerstein et al. (2003), how pupils connect with others determines their language learning ability and transmission of culture.

Collaboration, or helpful adaptation, is unquestionably important in language learning. According to McConnell (2000), language learning through socialisation "explains hazy ideas; develops basic reasoning abilities; provides a road for data sharing; develops relational abilities; provides a setting where students can learn in a social setting; and provides a spot for the approval of one's musings through discussion, multiple points of view, and contention." Developing learning forms by coordinating technology with learning is a trend that educators all around the world are following. Educators commonly use Twitter, blogs, Facebook, Youtube, or Flickr to help students with their writing. Through online innovation and condition, using social media in the writing process makes it more innovative and intuitive (Nichols, 2007).

All things considered, modern society expects today's pupils to be equipped with cutting-edge specialised skills and equipment that will enable them to "take an interest entirely out in the open, network, inventive, and monetary life" (New London Group, 2000). The trend encourages not just text creation but also social interaction. Computer-generated simulations and exercises are expanding opportunities for pupils to improve their use of the best language (Ranalli, 2008) The following are the outcomes of a study that confirms the usefulness of combining video-based blogs with ESL learning:

- 1) Learning open chatting was possible with video-based web blogging.
- 2) Learners' articulation, outer appearances, stance, and signals improved as a result of blogging.
- 3) Through association, students learnt how to blog and use sight and sound programming.
- 4) Students have the option of revisiting their mistakes on occasion by watching the film again.
- 5) Through self-assessment and within a group through friend comments and audits, the students learned how to operate without anybody else's input/herself (Shih, 2010).

Language learning and security are actually made available to everybody thanks to social media's vast, print-rich advanced condition. These ideas, which are brought together in this study, are intended to analyse the context of how social media affects English language acquisition. Consider these hypotheses to be true, and keep in mind that just a few tests have been conducted on them. This study attempts to shed some light on a relevant issue that impacts English learning in this nation. This expertise might aid in the dissemination of information on the influence of social media on English language learning.

A. Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to analyse the advantages, disadvantages, possibilities, and risks that social media presents in English language learning or acquisition in south India.

The following research issues will be addressed in this study:

1. What are the advantages of social media in terms of ELL?
2. What are the flaws in social media that negatively impact ELL?
3. What are the advantages of using social media in ELL?
4. What are the dangers that social media poses to ELL students?
5. What strategies may be learned from the analysis to optimise the use of social media in ELL?

B. Scope of the study and limitations

Only the benefits, flaws, possibilities, and risks of social media in English language learning in India are examined in this study.

English language learners and social media users, teachers, instructors, professors, and an expert in the field of Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages from India were among the participants in this study.

C. Research Design (Methodology)

Due to the numerous consequences of this study, a variety of elements were considered while selecting a design. The interpretative technique of research was chosen. To explore each component of this research, the participants' ideas and perspectives were synthesised using a thematic method.

The purpose of this case study was to give an in-depth investigation of the "how" and "why" of social media's influence on English language acquisition in a real-world environment. A SWOT matrix was specifically created to allow the researcher to study the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in order to offer emphasis. Because of its simplicity and efficacy, the SWOT analysis, a basic method often used in commercial organisations and systems, was used in this study (Pickton & Wright, 1998). The aforementioned technique was found to be the most suited for this since it lead the researcher to investigate key aspects of the study and achieve particular objectives.

D. A sampling of the study

English language teachers, instructors, and educators in junior high and senior high school with an English language learning background were included in this study. These were thought to be the most active users of social media and the persons in charge of teaching English at various educational institutions. This study employed qualitative research's purposeful sampling technique. The participants were chosen based on their skill and background in social media to supply the correct sort of information in the field of English language acquisition, and they were expected to meaningfully contribute knowledgeable views on the researcher's topic of choice.

An expert from the ELT professional organisation, one university professor, one ESL school instructor, one Senior High School English teacher, one Junior High School English teacher, one Elementary School teacher, and four Senior High School English language students were among the ten participants in this study, who represented each group of those involved in the teaching and learning of English in the country. The presence of a diverse group of participants aided in the collection of relevant data and the development of depth and breadth in the study topic.

E. Procedure for Data Collection

The information for this study was gathered through a written interview with the participants. The participants were contacted by the researcher using an online Facebook message service. The written interview guide was sent to the participants through email or the same messaging app. The participants provided all of their responses to the interview questions in writing to the researcher within a week or two. As a result, the participants had enough of time to organise their ideas and respond appropriately to the themes.

F. Analysis of Data

The data was analysed based on the themes that emerged throughout the study's execution. The topics, thoughts, or ideas that were stated at least three times by the participants will be considered. A SWOT analysis matrix was used for the participants to complete out to ensure that all of the study's components were covered and that all of the research questions were addressed.

III. DISCUSSIONS AND RESULTS

The SWOT analysis grid was utilised to quickly and accurately put all of the findings. The findings were used to answer the research question of this study a short time later. Every piece of information gathered in this study was processed with care, keeping in mind the nature of qualitative research. The findings of this study, as well as the different components that went into it, were considered as launching pads for further inquiries into this theme or pattern.

A. SWOT: S – Strengths

The data gathered revealed strengths that were taken into account in this study. These strengths have been identified by the participants as major characteristics in how social media profoundly influences English language acquisition. The majority of the participants' knowledge was based on the belief that English is regarded as a "global language" (Crystal, 2012), and that it is widely used by the majority of people throughout the world, similar to how it is used on most social media platforms.

Data, language documents, and vocabularies abound. The participants proved that social media are exceptional sources of up-to-date, vital material, such as news, online journals, wikis, and much more, all of which are published in English. In addition, social media provides all of the more engaging non-direct communications that attract all of their younger customers (Howe and Strauss, 2009). Despite the fact that it takes solid judgement on the part of each individual to determine what is legitimate and what is fake news, social media platforms provide massive amounts of information that are ready for public consumption. They also emphasise the importance of social media in shaping one's vocabulary and linguistic skills. Some of them mentioned the following: "For language learning, social media is a universally accessible and data-free hotspot. There is no compelling need to hire an English guide or enrol in expensive English schools."

"My own understanding is that I've grown attached to technology since I started binge-watching reviews and hardware teardowns, and I've developed a few vocabularies that few people are aware of, such as "gamut," and, interestingly enough, I was very hesitant to start convos or ask questions to various personas before I discovered the various types of social media. But today, once I have a problem, I go straight to my companions and different online gatherings and assistance centres; it has helped me build a relationship with the English language that most coursebooks have failed to do."

The introduction that social media provides with English language students occurs in a situation where these customers are enjoying, studying, and understanding the language more often.

To correspondence, affiliation, and partnership, make a presentation. Another piece of information provided by members adds to the concept of using social media, particularly social organising sites, to enhance human interaction. Because these sites, applications, or initiatives connect people, they also provide venues for correspondence, allowing people to practise the objective language of English.

The participants indicated "avenue for correspondence" as one of the social media's merits, according to their viewpoints.

"They can converse with a variety of people to enhance their English."

"In a broad premise, English language pupils develop relational abilities through social media networking association."

"It's important to present objective language to kids because they are regularly on the internet or checking their accounts."
 "Greater significant influence in applying the language in this manner creating more eagerness to study."

"It's interesting to remain in touch with old friends and acquaintances. It's a great way to sit and relax for a while."

"Teachers may offer information, encourage debate, and respond to questions; even the craze over hashtags can help teachers create singular/bunch endeavours that foster online dialogue among students."

Because many of these people grew up with these types of technology, it seemed natural for them to be proficient in their use. Whether they are sending text messages, posting on Facebook, Twitter, or Instagram, or playing online games, they have the chance to practise their English and provide information to others.

Social media, technology that has been installed on the globe where they grew up. Participants who identified as "digital natives" described the current generation as those who were born into a world of computers and high technology. All things considered, they suggest that these folks are more technologically savvy and adapt faster than their predecessors. Furthermore, these individuals receive a large number of presentations on English language works at an early age, resulting in higher language acquisition and learning. They believe that, because social media has been integrated into this cutting-edge world, language students will have easier access to a print-rich environment where learning English will be unquestionably reinforced. "Indeed, even youngsters at incredibly young ages may easily reach social media locations and learn the language by conversing with others," said one participant.

"When it comes to English language acquisition, the proper presentation of internet networking among teenagers may be really beneficial. Because technology, innovation, and social media are all there, youngsters may easily gain access to them."

"Interaction on social media is ingrained in today's cutting-edge society. Nowadays, kids may utilise Facebook, YouTube videos, and games for educational and communication purposes. Language learning and acquisition are always possible with this kind of innovation."

"Now, social media has become the new reality. Because they appeal to young people, they are suitable in language acquisition. Almost everyone now has a Facebook account. It's where they pick up new words and phrases from other people's posts.

B. SWOT: W – Weakness

Social media offers opportunities for language acquisition, and one of the most pressing problems is the type of language people acquire on the internet. Indecent conversations, repulsive content, and exclamations are only a few of the negatives of online networking that are affecting their audiences these days. Language students will pick up on them in their speaking and writing in general.

"A large portion of us need access to the Internet, many incessant online networking to express their conclusions as they are qualified for, and tonnes don't utilise the language effectively endangers the very language by spreading unessential and occasionally indecent phrasings that shouldn't be said on all accounts, it will spark a guilelessness among the watchers of their content as social media is ordinarily the group's decision of redistributing their content," one of the participants said.

Furthermore, due to the influence of social media, non-grammatical concepts, words, or articulations are becoming increasingly appropriate these days. Web languages, compressing, and shorter compositions, among other things, are altering the proper approach for collaboration and, as a result, producing communication breakdown. There is a lack of genuine linguistic contact. The eye to eye, individual element of correspondence is required in the social media cooperation technique. In a few social media sites, nonverbal communication, gestures, facial articulations, sentiments, and other nonverbal signs are weak, if not completely absent.

Writing abilities are dwindling. Contract employment, content informing, pictures, and web languages all grew in popularity with the rise of online living. The participants stated that these cutting-edge composing arrangements have a significant impact on the students' academic composition. The majority of people's formal writing include cyber slang and writing shortcuts.

C. SWOT: O – Opportunity

Access to native English speakers on a larger scale. Others saw social media as a stage where non-native English speakers may have more comprehensive access to social networking and correspondence. It was discovered that these advancements allow them to communicate with native English speakers or language professionals from all around the world. In addition, social media has been allowed for the promotion of online training or classes. Language students will also likely imitate or learn how the people they "follow" speak and write through video online diaries, tweets, Facebook posts, Instagram captions, digital recordings, music sounds and recordings, and much more.

For them, social media provides opportunities for language students to collaborate with experts in a variety of topics of interest and obtain the precise knowledge they want. "When skillfully arranged, live online classes may be rendered comparable to up close and personal learning," a few attendees said.

"Meeting someone with whom the learner may practise their L2 (second language) in this manner, allowing the student to use and speak L2."

"It's how I learn how English-speaking vloggers communicate. I've been told that I should speak like these people and use the language in class."

"ELLs have a lot of opportunities to form relationships with English-speaking or English-rehearsing people all around the world for social affiliation or contacts."

D. SWOT: T – Threat

Three hazards of social media in English language acquisition have been identified, according to information. First and foremost, social media disrupts learning and wastes time. The second source of correspondence issues is linguistic differences. Finally, there's the rise of web slangs and language subversion.

Distraction and time loss in the classroom are the result of this. The participants noticed that a huge percentage of them are occupied because of this generation's involvement in innovation, particularly with social media. Because technically skilled people in the media execute several activities and handle a lot of things at once, they will waste time on trivial matters.

Excessive time spent by individuals in long-distance informal communication destinations, internet games, video blogs, and other online networks has been seen to disrupt pupils who should be spending quality time in contemplation. These disruptions caused by social media pose significant risks to their customers' learning, focus, and overall health. Being sidetracked, however, social media users may be confused for a massive amount of information they handle at once, or they may become muddled up in their presentation of inappropriate items. A subset of the participants:

"Information may be covered up, and learning can be distracted or startled."

"When ELLs manage their time and choose the activities they need to do, they have less motivation to learn English. Unguided learning makes it easier to re-learn a language."

"Information overload or disarray if a student considers learning sources in an arbitrary or unorganised manner."

Contrasts in language that obstruct correspondence Another concern identified from the data was the possibility of correspondence breakdown due to linguistic differences among their users. Miscommunication is inescapable since the web and social media are areas where diverse sorts of cultures, foundations, and linguistic orientations collide. Language learning and acquisition can be hampered by languages other than English. As one of the participants pointed out:

"Because the Internet is used by people of various ethnicities and groups, the privilege words for one country may not be appropriate for another (for example, "bae" in Danish means "poop," while it is a word of intimacy in the Philippines.)"

"Not everything that is posted uses the objective language; instead, L1 is used."

The rise of web slangs and language subversion. The nonstop overflowing of slangs and subverting language on social media is the last of the dangers identified by the information. Others may have interpreted this as something positive or dynamic, but the majority of participants interpreted it as a danger to English language development.

"It turns out to be right if it's well-known to a large number of people."

"Continuous exposure to the language used by netizens has an impact on their learning technique." "When chatting on the internet, individuals may be more likely to utilise abbreviations or acronyms than genuine language."

IV. SUMMARY: FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS OF THE STUDY

A. Discussions

In terms of the study's goal, the researcher was guided to it by five research questions. Its goal was to identify the benefits, drawbacks, possibilities, and risks that social media presents in English language acquisition. This study also looked into ways for maximising the use of social media in English language acquisition.

B. Strengths of social media in ELL support

This study discovered that social media provides a number of advantages that either reinforce or aid English language acquisition among its users. Individuals nowadays obtain a lot of presentation or fathomable language input (Krashen, 1985) from information, writings, and vocabularies in social media destinations, so these qualities are seen (Bhatti, Shaheen, Kamal, & Ali, 2020). Individuals will also be able to use the language in any social media cooperation, contact, affiliation, or information exchange. Another strong link between social media and language acquisition is the fact that online life and other related advancements are deeply embedded in today's environment and culture.

C. Social Media Flaws have a Negative Impact on ELL

Information revealed social media's disadvantages, despite its benefits in English language acquisition. Despite the fact that some argue that social media makes a massive amount of data available to individuals, language novices are not immune to false data, obscenity in language, and grammar language compositions. In ELL, the lack of genuine human connection on computer screens was also mentioned as a drawback of social media. Finally, the new form of communication has impaired the writing talents of online networking users (Bhatti., Saad, & Gbadebo, 2020).

D. The Numerous Opportunities of Social Media in ELL

In terms of language acquisition, social media opens a few options. Individuals can get an opportunity to interact with native English speakers on a more comprehensive basis at these locations. Social networking also provides an unadorned 21st-century learning experience in areas such as correspondence, creativity, fundamental thinking, and collaborative effort. Learning through online networking has a bright future since technology is constantly evolving — it will always be a thing in the future.

E. The Threats that social media Poses to ELL

Three hazards of social media in language learning were shown by information. If not used correctly, internet networking can cause problems for language students. Students' time is wasted when they are exposed to unfavourable messages and information, which is not typical when they are immersed in increasingly practical topics. Individuals' distinctive languages spoken in online life can also interfere with English language acquisition and create a barrier to communication. Finally, the rise of cyber slang and undermining languages pose risks in language acquisition and may be dangerous if not properly addressed by educators.

V. RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY

In this study, it was discovered that social media had a good influence on users' English language acquisition. In any event, they may have disadvantages and risks that interfere with one's acquisition of proper English. Internet-based social media sites may be useful for providing up-to-date information, a large amount of language input, connections with native language speakers, and creative learning. Similar media, on the other hand, may engage language students with all of their trickery, unscholarly and grammatical content, nasty language, and phoney human associations.

Given that social media are rich sources of information, linguistic writings, and vocabularies, the scientist advises that instructors employ these major measures of information (Krashen, 1985) in online networking, whether in a genuine classroom setting or outside of formal learning. Because many language learners are overwhelmed by the vast amount of information available on the internet, including these media into language education might be beneficial. Teachers can also integrate actual messages from the social networking site in their classroom instructions, such as articles, noises, and recordings. The analyst also exhorts the language students or tenderfoots to design their online networks and systems so that they may collaborate with others and set up an on-the-web language network, with suitable adult supervision and the proper types of media. They have the potential to learn and master the target language through these types of linkages.

Furthermore, because these Net Genres, people who were born during the era of contemporary computers, are drawn to current technology, the research suggests that it be used in the teaching and learning process. According to the report, language students should use social media to have direct access to native English speakers on the internet. These same innovations are also essential to ensure that 21st Century talents like as correspondence, coordinated effort, ingenuity, fundamental thinking, and others are satisfied in the portions of the deals.

In order to deal with the dangers of social media in English language learning, it is suggested that students be taught to select the appropriate media and activate their channels to recognise what is fake and genuine data, what is healthy and what is not, as well as what is unscholarly or ungrammatical and sound language writings. Because actual human interaction is limited or absent on a virtual screen, language students should make it a point to teach themselves to communicate more face to face than when they are on the internet. The important elements of correspondence are used in this way, while correspondence breakdown is kept at a strategic distance.

Similarly, with the limitless condensed compositions, images, and web slangs that harm language learners' writing attitudes, it is recommended that teachers or adults educate their students about the dangers of these patterns, and that these children be directed to content-rich sources of sound English language.

Furthermore, these language students must have a limited amount of time to spend on social networking sites in order to avoid time waste and to devote quality time to ponders and other more beneficial activities. However, pupils would benefit greatly by selecting the appropriate media or material in order to avoid undermining languages and cyber slangs.

Furthermore, the danger of having so many other civilizations and dialects on the Internet besides English is an impediment to effective language learning. As a result, language students must strengthen their own channels by exposing themselves to a large amount of audible language input. They will be able to see which English is acceptable and which is not.

Furthermore, the use of social media and its concepts in language counselling in schools must be coordinated. To promote language learning in internet-based living destinations or gadgets, educational programmes, learning activities, and resources should be developed. Messages, websites, Wattpad, Facebook, Messenger, Tweeter, Instagram, Skype, and YouTube are all examples of well-known instruments that may be used efficiently for learner reading, writing, listening, speaking, and review and extension tasks.

This study might serve as a supplement to existing research or focus on any future research on English language acquisition through social media. More examiners are asked to dig further into this issue in order to advance this research. Continuous research or a data-driven study on the influence of social media on the language of India's young is encouraged.

An investigation of the disadvantages of the developing online living language in language training appears to necessitate the most thorough attention. Finally, further research is needed to inform the development of educational programmes, resources, and exercises for integrating social media into language teaching and learning. These study opportunities will contribute to shedding light on this under-researched topic.

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